

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 58

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 58:0 For the choir director; <i>set to</i> †Al-tashheth. A °Mikhtam of David.</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַח אֶל־תְּשִׁיחַ Psa. 58:1</p>
<p>Psa. 58:1 Do you indeed ¹ speak righteousness, O ² gods?</p>	<p>לְדָוִד מִכְתָּם : ² הָאֱמֹנִים</p>
<p>Do you ^a judge ³ uprightly, O sons of men?</p>	<p>אֵלֶם צְדָק תְּדַבְּרוּן מִיִּשְׁרָיִם</p>
<p>² No, in heart you ^a work unrighteousness;</p>	<p>תִּשְׁפֹּטוּ בְּנֵי אָדָם : ³ אֶרֶץ־</p>
<p>On earth you ^b weigh out the violence of your hands.</p>	<p>בְּלֵב עֹלֹת תִּפְעֹלֶיךָ בְּאָרֶץ</p>
<p>³ The wicked are estranged ^a from the womb;</p>	<p>חַמְס יְדֵיכֶם תִּפְלֹסוּן : ⁴ זָרוּ</p>
<p>These who speak lies ^b go astray from ¹ birth.</p>	<p>רְשָׁעִים מִרַחֵם תָּעוּ מִבֶּטֶן</p>
<p>⁴ They have venom like the ^a venom of a serpent;</p>	<p>וּבְרִי כָזָב : ⁵ חַמַּת־לָמוּ</p>
<p>Like a deaf cobra that stops up its ear,</p>	<p>כְּדַמוֹת חַמַּת־נָחָשׁ כְּמוֹ־פִתְוִן</p>
<p>⁵ So that it ^a does not hear the voice of ^{1b} charmers,</p>	<p>חֵרֶשׁ יֵאָטֵם אָזְנוֹ : ⁶ אֲשֶׁר</p>
<p>Or a skillful caster of spells.</p>	<p>לֹא־יִשְׁמַע לְקוֹל מְלַחְשִׁים</p>
<p>Psa. 58:6 O God, ^a shatter their teeth in their mouth;</p>	<p>חֹזֵר חֲבָרִים מִחַכָּם : ⁷</p>
<p>Break out the fangs of the young lions, O LORD.</p>	<p>אֵלֹהִים הֲרֹס־שִׁנֵּימוּ בְּפִימוּ</p>
<p>⁷ Let them ^a flow away like water that runs off;</p>	<p>מִלְּתַעֲוֹת כְּפִיָּרִים נִתְּץ </p>
<p>When he ^{1b} aims his arrows, let them be as ² headless shafts.</p>	<p>יִהְיֶה : ⁸ יִמָּאֲסוּ כְּמוֹ־מַיִם</p>
<p>⁸ Let them be as a snail which ¹ melts away as it goes along,</p>	<p>יִתְהַלְכוּ־לָמוּ יְדִרְךָ תִּצּוּ</p>
<p>Like the ^a miscarriages of a woman which never see the sun.</p>	<p>[חֲצִיּוֹ] כְּמוֹ יִתְמַלְּלוּ : ⁹ כְּמוֹ</p>
	<p>שֶׁבֶלֹל תִּמָּס יִהְיֶה גִּפְלֵ אִשָּׁת בֶּל־תִּזּוּ שָׁמֶשׁ : ¹⁰</p>
	<p>בְּטָרֵם יִבִּינּוּ סִירְתֵיכֶם אֲטָר</p>

⁹ Before your ^apots can feel *the fire of* thorns

He will ^bsweep them away with a whirlwind, the ¹green and the burning alike.

Psa. 58:10 The ^arighteous will rejoice when he ^bsees the vengeance;

He will ^cwash his feet in the blood of the wicked.

¹¹ And men will say, “Surely there is a ^{1a}reward for the righteous;

Surely there is a God who ^bjudges ²on earth!”

כְּמוֹתַי כְּמוֹתֵי חָרוֹן יִשְׁעֵינִי׃

11 יִשְׁמַח צְדִיק בִּי־תוֹה נֶקֶם

פְּעָמָיו יִרְחֹץ בַּדָּם הַרְשָׁע׃

12 וַיֹּאמֶר אָדָם אֶךְ־פְּרִי

לְצְדִיק אֶךְ־יֵשׁ־אֱלֹהִים

שֹׁפְטִים בָּאָרֶץ׃

References

Psalm 57:0

†Lit *Do Not Destroy*

°Possibly, *Epigrammatic Poem* or *Atonement Psalm*

^1 Sam 22:1; 24:3

Psalm 57:1

^aPs 2:12; 34:22

^bRuth 2:12; Ps 17:8; 36:7; 63:7; 91:4

^cIs 26:20

Psalm 57:2

^aPs 138:8

Psalm 57:3

¹Or *snaps at*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

³Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 18:16; 144:5, 7

^bPs 56:2

^cPs 25:10; 40:11

Psalm 57:4

^aPs 35:17; 58:6

^bProv 30:14

^cPs 55:21; 59:7; 64:3; Prov 12:18

Psalm 57:5

^aPs 57:11; 108:5

Psalm 57:6

¹Or *spread*

^aPs 10:9; 31:4; 35:7; 140:5

^bPs 145:14

^cPs 7:15

^dProv 26:27; 28:10; Eccl 10:8

Psalm 57:7

^aPs 57:7-11; 108:1-5

^bPs 112:7

Psalm 57:8

^aPs 16:9; 30:12

^bPs 150:3

Psalm 57:9

¹Lit *peoples*

^aPs 108:3

Psalm 57:10

¹Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 36:5; 103:11; 108:4

Psalm 57:11

^aPs 57:5; 108:5

Targum

Psa. 58:1 For praise; concerning the distress in the time when David said, “Do no harm”; composed by David, humble and innocent. ² In very truth are you silent, O righteous ones, in the time of strife? It is fitting that you speak righteousness, that you judge uprightly the sons of men. ³ But, O wicked, wherefore do you commit iniquity in the heart, wherefore do your hands establish crime on the earth? ⁴ The wicked have become strangers from birth; those who utter falsehood have gone astray from the womb. ⁵ Poison is theirs like the poison of the serpent; like the deaf adder that stops up his ears. ⁶ Lest it should accept the words of the wizards, the charmers of snakes; he is wiser than those who cast spells. ⁷ O God, smash their teeth in their mouth; and shatter the fangs of the lions’ offspring, O LORD. ⁸ Let them dissolve in their sins; like water, let them flow away; and he draws arrows at them, and they will be cut in pieces. ⁹ Like the crawling snail whose path is disgusting, like the abortion and the mole who are blind and have not seen the sun; ¹⁰ Before the soft wicked become as hard as thorns, while they are moist, while they are like unripe fruit, may he destroy them by the storm wind. ¹¹ The righteous will rejoice, for he has seen retribution on them; he will wash his feet in the blood of the wicked man. ¹² And the sons of men will say, “Truly, there is a good reward for the righteous, truly there is a God whose judgments extend to the earth.”

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction and Superscript

In the previous Psalm, David did not allow his men to kill Saul when he entered the cave they were hiding in. David allowed Saul to live and cut off a piece of his cloak. David hoped that this demonstrated to Saul his loyalty. This Psalm talks about Saul's underlings who conspired to destroy David's goodwill.

Midrash Shocheh Tov says that Saul's underlings came to him and argued that David was not a righteous man. If David had killed Saul in the cave, David knew he would have been torn limb by limb.

Talmud tractate Yerushalmi Sotah 1:8 says that Saul's leading general, Abner claimed that Saul's garment tore on a thorn, and David recovered the piece of apparel and was using it to trick Saul.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. Let not destruction come. A tenet by David.

Verse one

הַאִמֵּנָם (haom'nam) – means “indeed.” This word can also mean “in truth.”

When the **י** is added, it becomes a question, “Is it true?” or “Is it truly so?”

תִּשְׁפֹּטוּ (teesh'p'tu) – means “to judge.” This word does not necessarily mean legal enforcement of justice based on a witness. Instead, it is used to indicate a social judgment.

Is silence truly just when you should speak instead? When should you judge the sons of man in equity?

Verse two

What constrains a person from speaking the truth against lawlessness?

Even with your hearts, you commit atrocities. You weigh out the wrong of your hands in the land.

Verses three, four, and five

The preceding verses were a reproach to those who could have acted to put a stop to evil. David charges them with being accomplices in the wrong that has been perpetrated because they have failed to teach, warn, or remonstrate with sinners.

And if the lawless are estranged [from good] from the mother's womb, if liars go astray from birth.

If their raging is like the rage of a serpent, like a deaf viper which closes its ear,

Which does not harken to the voice of the charmers, of the most cunning binder of spells.

Verse six

David calls upon all qualified men to wield their power to prevent evil. There were no men available.

Then you are in God's place! Break their teeth in their mouths; to destroy the teeth of lions is the work of the LORD with loving kindness.

Verse seven

Society makes itself an accomplice to all evil in this world as long as it accepts crime. Also, society's acceptance of all immorality will bring its downfall. This is seen today when woke District Attorneys blame victims for perpetrators' crimes. Today's society has decided to consider a lot of the immorality of the woke crowd acceptable. This can become society's downfall.

Despised, they would melt away like water; they would steal away even if one of them aims his arrows; it is as though they crumbled away.

Verse eight

The next verses are the finishing remarks of the description of the gradual disappearance of evil that would be brought about by the intervention of righteous people. Unfortunately, in today's society, the woke are excellent trolls. They know how to attack anyone who opposes their immoral changes to society. This creates the silent majority who will have to one day rise up against evil. When David was being chased by Saul, many people wanted to stand for David but knew they would be executed by Saul. Therefore, they did not come forward until Saul's death.

Even as the snail which melts and slithers away, as the stillbirth of a woman, both of which have never seen the sun.

Verse nine

Rabbi Hirsch said that this is a difficult verse to interpret. He offered that we need to muster all the forces of good for the intervention against evil. Evil in Saul's day was intense and shown through Saul's madness to kill David. David was loyal to Saul and was his son-in-law. That did not stop evil from conquering Saul. It is going to take all of the goodness of the world to stop the evil that has taken over.

Before your thinner thorns can reveal the brier as if it were alive, as if evil incarnate is sweeping one away with a whirlwind.

Verse ten

The word "blood" in this verse denotes the vengeance that was threatening wicked people. There is no call for killing in the Psalm. Therefore, blood denotes vengeance. David tells the righteous that they must drive away the wicked. The righteous traits will help other people resolve their lives and make themselves pure. Evil people can be turned by the acts and words of the righteous.

But the righteous person shall rejoice when they foresee vengeance; they shall keep their own steps all the more pursued at the time of the destruction of the wicked.

Verse eleven

Righteousness can offer a reward on Earth or later in Heaven.

And men shall say, "Indeed there is still a reward for the righteous; there are still those who act in God's place, as judges in the land."

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. Let not destruction come. A tenet by David.

Is silence truly just when you should speak instead? When should you judge the sons of man in equity?

Even with your hearts, you commit atrocities. You weigh out the wrong of your hands in the land.

And if the lawless are estranged [from good] from the mother's womb, if liars go astray from birth.

If their raging is like the rage of a serpent, like a deaf viper which closes its ear,

Which does not harken to the voice of the charmers, of the most cunning binder of spells.

Then you are in God's place! Break their teeth in their mouths; to destroy the teeth of lions is the work of the LORD with loving kindness.

Despised, they would melt away like water; they would steal away even if one of them aims his arrows; it is as though they crumbled away.

Even as the snail which melts and slithers away, as the stillbirth of a woman, both of which have never seen the sun.

Before your thinner thorns can reveal the brier as if it were alive, as if evil incarnate is sweeping one away with a whirlwind.

But the righteous person shall rejoice when they foresee vengeance; they shall keep their own steps all the more pursued at the time of the destruction of the wicked.

And men shall say, “Indeed there is still a reward for the righteous; there are still those who act in God’s place, as judges in the land.”

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

